

Database: Europe PMC
 URL: <https://europepmc.org/>
 Date Searched: 10.06.2024

#	Searches	Results	Note
1	(Title:("gen-AI" OR GenAI OR "Generative-AI" OR "generative-artificial-intelligence" OR "Pretrained-Transformer" OR "Pretrained-Transformers" OR "general-language-model" OR "general-language-models" OR "general-purpose-LLM" OR "general-purpose-LLMs" OR "large language model" OR "large language models" OR "large-pretrained-language-model" OR "large-pretrained-language-models" OR GPT4ALL OR chatgpt OR gpt OR chatbot*) OR Abstract:("gen-AI" OR GenAI OR "Generative-AI" OR "generative-artificial-intelligence" OR "Pretrained-Transformer" OR "Pretrained-Transformers" OR "general-language-model" OR "general-language-models" OR "general-purpose-LLM" OR "general-purpose-LLMs" OR "large language model" OR "large language models" OR "large-pretrained-language-model" OR "large-pretrained-language-models" OR GPT4ALL OR chatgpt OR gpt OR chatbot*) OR Title:((claude OR llama) AND (ai OR llm OR language-model*)) OR Title:((Gemini OR google-BARD) AND (ai OR llm OR google OR language-model*)) OR Abstract:((claude OR llama) AND (ai OR llm OR language-model*)) OR Abstract:((Gemini OR google-BARD) AND (ai OR llm OR google OR language-model*)) OR Title:(llm AND ai) OR Abstract:(llm AND ai)	12'778	
2	(Title:("identify-literature" OR "literature-screening" OR "literature-selection" OR "study-selection" OR "select-literature" OR "screening-title" OR "screening-titles" OR "title-screening" OR "abstract-screening" OR "screen-title" OR "screen-titles" OR "literature-filtration" OR "title-abstract" OR "screen-article" OR "screen-articles" OR "Title-and-abstract" OR "Title-and-abstracts" OR ((screening OR screen*) AND (review* OR "meta-analysis" OR "meta-analyses" OR "evidence-synthesis" OR "evidence-syntheses"))) OR ((selection) AND (research-evidence)) OR Abstract:("identify-literature" OR "literature-screening" OR "literature-selection" OR "study-selection" OR "select-literature" OR "screening-title" OR "screening-titles" OR "title-screening" OR "abstract-screening" OR "screen-title" OR "screen-titles" OR "literature-filtration" OR "title-abstract" OR "screen-article" OR "screen-articles" OR "Title-and-abstract" OR "Title-and-abstracts" OR ((screening OR screen*) AND (review* OR "meta-analysis" OR "meta-analyses" OR "evidence-synthesis" OR "evidence-syntheses")) OR ((selection) AND (research-evidence))))	201'276	
3	(Title:("Pretrained-Transformer" OR "Pretrained-Transformers" OR "general-language-model" OR "general-language-models" OR "general-purpose-LLM" OR "general-purpose-LLMs" OR "gen-AI" OR GenAI OR "Generative-AI" OR "generative-artificial-intelligence" OR "large language model" OR "large language models" OR "large-pretrained-language-model" OR "large-pretrained-language-models" OR GPT4ALL OR chatgpt OR gpt OR chatbot* OR ((claude OR llama) AND (ai OR llm OR language-model*)) OR ((Gemini OR google-BARD) AND (ai OR llm OR google OR language-model*)) OR (llm AND ai)) OR Abstract:("Pretrained-Transformer" OR "Pretrained-Transformers" OR "general-language-model" OR "general-language-models" OR "general-purpose-LLM" OR "general-purpose-LLMs" OR "gen-AI" OR GenAI OR "Generative-AI" OR "generative-artificial-intelligence" OR "large language model" OR "large language models" OR "large-pretrained-language-model" OR "large-pretrained-language-models" OR GPT4ALL OR chatgpt OR gpt OR chatbot* OR ((claude OR llama) AND (ai OR llm OR "language-model" OR "language-models")) OR ((Gemini OR google-BARD) AND (ai OR llm OR google OR "language-model" OR "language-models")) OR (llm AND ai))) AND (Title:("identify-literature" OR "literature-screening" OR "literature-selection" OR "study-selection" OR "select-literature" OR "screening-title" OR "screening-titles" OR "title-screening" OR "abstract-screening" OR "screen-title" OR "screen-titles" OR "literature-filtration" OR "title-abstract" OR "screen-article" OR "screen-articles" OR "Title-and-abstract" OR "Title-and-abstracts" OR ((screening OR screen*) AND (review* OR "meta-analysis" OR "meta-analyses" OR "evidence-synthesis" OR "evidence-syntheses"))) OR ((selection) AND (research-evidence))) OR Abstract:("identify-literature" OR "literature-screening" OR "literature-selection" OR "study-selection" OR "select-literature" OR "screening-title" OR "screening-titles" OR "title-screening" OR "abstract-screening" OR "screen-title" OR "screen-titles" OR "literature-filtration" OR "title-abstract" OR "screen-article" OR "screen-articles" OR "Title-and-abstract" OR "Title-and-abstracts" OR ((screening OR screen*) AND (review* OR "meta-analysis" OR "meta-analyses" OR "evidence-synthesis" OR "evidence-syntheses")) OR ((selection) AND (research-evidence))))	246	
4	#3 AND (SRC:PPR)	143	filtered
5	#4 AND (FIRST_PDATE:[2022 TO 2024])	141	filtered

Topic: Evaluating LLMs for Literature Screening: A Systematic Review of Sensitivity and Workload Reduction

Database: Web of Science

URL: <https://www.webofscience.com/#advancedSearch/>

Date Searched: 10.06.2024

#	Searches	Results	Note
1	TS=(gen-AI OR GenAI OR Generative-AI OR generative-artificial-intelligence OR General-Pretrained-Transformer* OR generative-pretrained-transformer* OR general-language-model* OR general-purpose-LLM* OR large-language-model* OR large-pretrained-language-model* OR GPT4ALL OR chatgpt OR gpt OR chatbot* OR ((claude OR llama) NEAR/3 (ai OR llm OR language-model*)) OR ((Gemini OR google-BARD) NEAR/3 (ai OR llm OR google OR language-model*)) OR (llm AND ai))	19'555	
2	TS=(identify-literature* OR literature-screening OR literature-selection* OR study-selection* OR select-literature* OR screening-title* OR screen-title* OR literature-filtration* OR title-abstract* OR title-screening OR abstract-screening OR screen-article* OR Title-and-abstract* OR ((screening OR screen*) AND (review* OR meta-analy* OR evidence-synthes*)) OR ((selection) NEAR/3 (research-evidence*))	175'688	
3	#1 AND #2	130	
6	#5 filtered by index date 2022-01-01 TO 2024-12-31	107	

Topic: Evaluating LLMs for Literature Screening: A Systematic Review of Sensitivity and Workload Reduction

Database: Embase (Elsevier)

URL: <https://www.embase.com/#advancedSearch/>

Date Searched: 10.06.2024

#	Searches	Results	Note
1	generative artificial intelligence'/exp OR (gen-AI OR GenAI OR Generative-AI OR generative-artificial-intelligence OR General-Pretrained-Transformer* OR generative-pretrained-transformer* OR general-language-model* OR general-purpose-LLM* OR large-language-model* OR large-pretrained-language-model* OR GPT4ALL OR chatgpt OR gpt OR chatbot*):ti,ab,kw,de OR ((claude OR llama) NEAR/3 (ai OR llm OR language-model*)):ti,ab OR ((Gemini OR google-BARD) NEAR/3 (ai OR llm OR google OR language-model*)):ti,ab OR (llm:ti,ab AND ai:ti,ab)	14'366	
2	(identify-literature* OR literature-screening OR literature-selection* OR study-selection* OR select-literature* OR screening-title* OR screen-title* OR literature-filtration* OR title-abstract* OR title-screening OR abstract-screening OR screen-article* OR Title-and-abstract* OR ((screening OR screen*) AND (review* OR meta-analy* OR evidence-synthes*)) OR ((selection) NEAR/3 (research-evidence*)):ti,ab	172'924	
3	#1 AND #2	104	
6	#5 AND [2022-2024]/py	88	
7	(38214966 OR 38539117 OR 38484744 OR 38768452):ui OR L2028778	5	
8	#6 AND #7	5	

Topic: Evaluating LLMs for Literature Screening: A Systematic Review of Sensitivity and Workload Reduction

Database: Medline (OVID)

URL: Ovid MEDLINE(R) <1946 to May Week 5 2024>

Date Searched: 10.06.2024

#	Searches	Results	Note
1	(gen-AI OR GenAI OR Generative-AI OR generative-artificial-intelligence OR General-Pretrained-Transformer* OR generative-pretrained-transformer* OR general-language-model* OR general-purpose-LLM* OR large-language-model* OR large-pretrained-language-model* OR GPT4ALL OR chatgpt OR gpt OR chatbot*).ti,ab,kw,kf OR ((claude OR llama) ADJ3 (ai OR llm OR language-model*)).ti,ab OR ((Gemini OR google-BARD) ADJ3 (ai OR llm OR google OR language-model*)).ti,ab OR (llm.ti,ab AND ai.ti,ab)	7'658	
2	(identify-literature* OR literature-screening OR literature-selection* OR study-selection* OR select-literature* OR screening-title* OR screen-title* OR literature-filtration* OR title-abstract* OR title-screening OR abstract-screening OR screen-article* OR Title-and-abstract* OR ((screening OR screen*) AND (review* OR meta-analy* OR evidence-synthes*)) OR ((selection) ADJ3 (research-evidence*))).ti,ab	139'574	
3	#1 AND #2	58	
4	limit 3 to yr="2022 - 2024"	41	

Topic: Evaluating LLMs for Literature Screening: A Systematic Review of Sensitivity and Workload Reduction

Databases	Results	Date
Embase	88	10.06.2024
Medline	41	10.06.2024
Web of Science	107	10.06.2024
EPMC	141	10.06.2024
Total	377	
Duplicates	97	Covidence
To screen	280	